

Research Paper

**Classroom Organization and Students' Involvement in Public Secondary Schools
in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19555271>

Received 05, 04 2026; Accepted 11 04, 2026© The author(s)2026. Published with open
access at www.rapidjournals.com

ABSTRACT: This study examined the impact of collaborative classroom management strategies on teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. A descriptive survey research design was employed, and five research questions were formulated to guide the investigation. Using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique, a total of 140 teachers—comprising 51 males and 89 females—were selected from public secondary schools in the area. Data were collected using a researcher-designed instrument titled Collaborative Classroom Management Strategies and Teacher Job Performance Questionnaire (CCMSTJPQ), structured on a four-point Likert scale. The instrument was validated by experts in Educational Management from Niger Delta University and tested for reliability using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.828, confirming a high level of internal consistency. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to analyze the responses, with a criterion mean of 2.50 set for interpretation. Findings revealed that collaborative strategies such as peer feedback and support, teamwork and communication, and knowledge sharing and resource exchange significantly influenced teacher job performance. These practices were found to foster an engaging, supportive, and motivating teaching environment, contributing to professional growth and enhanced instructional delivery. The study concluded that implementing collaborative classroom strategies positively impacts teacher effectiveness and job performance. It recommended that school administrators institutionalize peer observation, encourage collaborative teamwork, and facilitate knowledge sharing platforms among teachers to build a cohesive, high-performing teaching workforce.

Keywords: Collaborative strategies, teacher performance, peer feedback, teamwork, knowledge sharing

I. Introduction

A classroom that is effectively organized equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to adapt easily to teaching/learning programmes and enhance comprehensibility insightfulness. Students engage in classroom collaborative activities and discussions, when they like how the layout patterns of their classroom are arranged coupled with easy access to learning materials. Furthermore, students' participation in the teaching/learning process, are reinforced their engagement that fosters autonomy and accountability through classroom organization support. Classroom organization enable teachers to maintain discipline and build productive learning environment for students (Hu et al., 2025). Classroom organization is the measures used by teachers to manage their classroom (Halidane et al., 2024). It includes unique features of the environment (availability of physical resources and the organization of such resources for students use) and ideal elements of how time is used throughout the

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day) (Cutler et al., 2023). Classroom organization is the teacher's ability to manage routine transitions, creating clear expectations and rules to effectively engage students to minimize disruptive behaviours in the classroom. The organization of the classroom is an important strategy for the successful functioning of students learning opportunities and outcomes (Petkou et al., 2025). Clear expectations and rules can create social skills that enhance healthy relationships and promote positive classroom environment (Niu et al., 2025). It enables students to navigate complex social environments effectively (Grover et al., 2020). Students who have strong communication skills are better able to listen intently, share ideas clearly, and work together with teachers and peers (Qadeer et al., 2025). Teaching and learning and learners' social skills enhancement cannot take place if the classroom is not managed effectively (Ahmed, 2024). Effective behaviour management can enhance immediate feedbacking to become a powerful tool that can help students to understand what they did well and what they need to do in order to progress further (Ahmad et al., 2025). Teacher can use effective behaviour compliance to manage students' behaviour by creating a positive environment for learning where all students feel comfortable and safe (Ubah, 2025). It gives students information they need so they can understand where they are in their learning and what to do next, the cognitive factor (Gledo, 2025). Feedbacks like comments given in writing, such as those given on assignments and tests, give a form of record that the student can go through to strengthen recall (Kolachi et al., 2024).

II. Statement of the Problem

The National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014; Section 1, No. 6a, p.2), affirmed "the development of the individual (students) into a morally sound, patriotic and effective citizen". This all-round development of the individual stressed the need to engage students meaningfully, especially in the classroom. However, the investigator observed that students in public secondary schools' in Bayelsa State reluctantly participate in class discussions, they have issues engaging in groupwork and experience conflict in peer interaction; consequently, it was also observed that teachers' inability to cope with unexpected situations in the classroom has affected how they manage classroom diversity and conflict with students which have hindered student engagement in the classrooms. Contemporary method of using clear expectation and rules and adaptation to learning to effectively engage students in the classrooms have not been fully researched. Students' experience poor academic achievement due to their lack of engagement in classroom management. There are no logical reasons why a lot of public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State are not effectively engaging their students to be able to manage their classrooms successfully.

III. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between classroom organization and students' involvement in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess the relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area.
2. Investigate the relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area.

IV. Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area?
2. What is the relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area?

V. Research Hypotheses

Three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of statistical significance:

Ho1 There is no significant relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area.

Ho2 There is no significant relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area.

V. Review of Related Literature

a. Clear Expectations and Rules

Classroom expectations are clearly defined explanations of behavioural and classroom performance that help create a consistent and safe learning environment (Croce & Salter, 2022). Setting expectations and clear rules helps students understand what behaviour is acceptable (Oruikor et al., 2023). Students' adherence to and maintenance of the classroom rules are the responsibility of the teachers (Khaliq et al., 2025). Teachers use a number of strategies for establishing and enforcing clear expectations and rules, talking supportively, explaining the consequences of behaviour, offering choices, sending timeouts (Shanshan, 2024). Setting clear and consistent rules and expectations will enable teachers need to set concrete expectations about student behaviour at the beginning of the school year or learning session. These rules should be conveyed in a firm but fair manner, and it is important to enforce the consequences consistently (Elliott, 2023). Clear expectations and rules help to foster positive relationships and implement rules to create an organized, disciplined and engaging environment (Suleiman et al., 2025). Clear and consistent rules help create an orderly classroom, as students understand expectations and consequences (Adeyemo, 2019). Establishing clear rules and expectations helps students understand boundaries while promoting positive behaviour. This structured environment is essential for fostering discipline and self-control skills that are crucial for personal development (Oni et al., 2025). Some other way of creating a conducive learning environment include establishing clear expectations and rules for behaviour that can help prevent disruptive and unsafe behaviour in the classroom (Ogalo et al., 2024). Setting expectations is a way to define appropriate classroom behaviour and to build consistency and structure among students (Croce & Salter, 2022).

Teachers who establish clear rules and expectations, provide timely feedback and use positive reinforcement tend to cultivate a structured learning environment conducive to academic success (Gbadamosi, 2025). Teachers can help students to develop and inculcate sound moral rectitude and values through obedience and conformity to public secondary schools' rules and regulations (Nwakanma, 2025). Setting clear, communicating rules and expectations for behaviour, positive reinforcement using praise and rewards to encourage desired behaviours and achievements, and behavioural interventions in implementing strategies to address and correct disruptive or inappropriate behaviours are used in classroom management (Evans et al., 2024). Setting expectations guides students' behaviours in class and instill in them discipline and respect for others (Agim et al., 2025). Consistent application of rules helps students understand expectations and consequences, reducing the likelihood of disruptive behaviours (Ekundayo, & Alade, 2025). When students know what is expected of them, they are more likely to follow rules and meet expectations (Makala, 2025). A student is expected to obey the school rules and regulations and be committed to academics being the primary duty in the school (Olofin, 2025). Teachers who set clear rules and expectations while allowing students to participate in decision-making foster a more conducive learning environment (Olayinka & Ridwan, 2025). The teacher should be able to communicate the rules and expectations of the class and make the students know the consequences of their actions (Anyaeji, 2023). Setting clear, consistent, and age-appropriate rules at the beginning of the school term helps establish boundaries and expectations. When students understand what is expected of them, they are more likely to follow classroom procedures and routines. Involving students in the creation of these rules can also encourage ownership and accountability (Oruikor et al., 2023).

Establishing rules and expectations involves setting clear classroom expectations to promote a respectful and productive learning environment (Okaforcha & Okeke 2020). Managing the classroom involves all actions and strategies adopted and applied by teachers to keep the students on-task in the class. These strategies involve establishing clear expectations and rules, maintaining consistency in enforcing these rules, and implementing proactive measures to prevent disruptions (Akulue et al., 2025). The environment the teacher creates in the classroom includes the choice of the teacher on rules and expectations (Ukaumunna et al., 2025).

b. Effective Behaviour Management

Behaviour management is the process which support learners to make positive choice that are helpful for learning (Baidya & Das, 2024). Behaviour management is part of the school system which represents an extrinsic motivator (Arthur & Bradley, 2023). It is an important step in outcomes in general and special education for all pupils and students (Nwankwoala, 2021). Behaviour Management is implementing strategies to address inappropriate behaviour and maintain order within the classroom (Ojimba, 2019; Ehigiator & Ucheagwu-Okoye, 2021). Effective behaviour management promotes respect and minimises disruptions (Oruikor et al., 2023). Student behaviour management is one of the contemporary problems faced by managers of schools (Runhare & Mushayi, 2024). A key strategy for improving behaviour management in schools is to implement clear and consistent methods (Kern & Wehmeyer, 2021). Effective behaviour management is crucial for creating positive learning environments (Darling-Hammond & DePaoli, 2020). Effective behaviour management includes strategies to prevent and handle misbehaviour. Addressing behavioural issues in classrooms, for instance, disruptive behaviours such as shouting and bullying not only hinder individual academic growth but also affect the overall classroom climate (Lannie et al., 2021).

Issue of academic dishonesty raises concerns about the long-term effects of disciplinary measures in educational settings and emphasizes the need for more effective behaviour management strategies (Pastolero & Dulin, 2025). It has been observed that corporal punishment does very little to promote long-term behaviour change but rather results in escalation of violence (Akyina, 2024; Vargo & Gushanas, 2023). Behaviour management not only makes students well-disciplined but also nurturing their social and emotional development. It makes them able to express themselves appropriately and more resilient (Baidya & Das, 2024). Teacher development is crucial for improving behaviour management in schools (Haßler et al., 2020). This systematic approach enhances teachers' skills through various training methods and collaborative learning (Sims & Fletcher-Wood, 2020; Lazarides et al., 2020). By equipping teachers to engage all learners, it helps reduce disruptive behaviour, fostering a safe and productive learning environment (Stevenson et al., 2020). Moreover, regular skill refinement allows for learner-centred lessons (Meesuk et al., 2020) and programmes like positive behavioural interventions and supports (PBIS) effectively enhance proactive behaviour management techniques (Simonsen et al., 2021). Parents active participation in their children's education is vital for behaviour management. This entails communicating with teachers, participation in school activities, and support with homework (Yulianti et al., 2022). Such likely involvement improves both academic performance and behaviour (Anastasiou & Papagianni, 2020; Kelty & Wakabayashi, 2020; Berkowitz et al., 2021; Oranga et al., 2023). Parents should also be involved to ensures alignment with community values, fostering a respectful atmosphere where learners feel valued and accountable (Sulthani & Thoifah, 2022). Clear communication of these values is essential for effective behaviour management.

c. Social Interaction Skills

Interaction is the process of constructing a meaningful exchange of information and ideas among more than two people (Baber, 2022). Interaction is a psychosomatic impression of the total process of developing a pedagogically meaningful exchange of constant contact between more than two people (Azmat & Ahmad, 2022). It is the central core of learning experience and a key factor for positive student learning outcome (Alqurashi, 2019). Interaction plays an important role in the development of students learning outcome (Mehall, 2020). Social interaction is the primary key to all social life (Putri et al., 2022). Social interactions are powerful determinants of learning (Shamay-Tsoory, 2022).

Social interaction is the interaction between students and teachers (Azmat & Ahmad, 2022). Social interaction is important to various aspects of students' life, such as well-being (Lee et al., 2020) and mental health (Li et al., 2020), self-esteem (Harris & Orth, 2020). Social interactions that create emotionally positive environment are categorised as socio-emotional interactions (Isohätälä et al., 2020). Students need to learn and master social skills to create and maintain social interactions (Kalmar et al., 2022). The school setting provides an extremely valuable platform for observing, analyzing, and affecting social interaction since it represents the most important place for social interaction among students (García-Carrión et al., 2019). Social intimacy is a part of social interaction where a person feels comfortable sharing their ideas and thoughts with the people around (Baber, 2022). Change in social interaction in turn could have an impact on the experience of social relatedness and friendships (Ellinger et al., 2023). Social interaction in the classroom is a reflection of academic synergy (Isohätälä et al., 2020). Positive social interactions can reduce stress levels and social isolation, which in turn can contribute to improved academic performance. Additionally, social interaction improves new student orientation programmes (Mohzana, 2024).

d. Immediate Feedback Strategies

Feedback is an information provided by classroom teachers about their students' performance or technical knowledge (Oke & Ijdshs, 2023). Feedback is a procedure where teachers allow students know about their skills and assess their performance in order to advance to the next level of academic endeavour. Feedback is crucial to teaching and learning activities (Bucchiarone, 2022) and it is key to effective learning (Miao, 2023). A learner consciously approaches the learning strategy through immediate feedback (Sadovets et al., 2022). Immediate and frequent feedback maintains the effectiveness of the learning process as well as picture how learners get to engage in the activities (Ariffin et al., 2022). Immediate feedback allows the students to determine their progress in the course and increases their desire to continue (Doney, 2019). Immediate feedback is a strategy used to make teaching and learning more effective by encouraging students to work hard and succeed in school (Oke & Ijdshs, 2023). Timely feedback is often help to inform learners that they were making progress (Zhan et al., 2022). Teachers observed that students given immediate feedback demonstrates improved performance than those students who receive delayed feedback (Osipovskaya & Miakotnikova, 2020). Immediate feedback helps students gain insight into their goals and follow the path to their success (Hassan et al., 2021). Feedback from the teacher and peers is essential to develop problem-solving skills and developing a perception of change as a possibility for growth (Montiel-Ruiz et al., 2023). Rewards can be used as a feedback device for learning activities (Park & Kim, 2023). Effective teachers use a range of teaching techniques, adapt lessons to the needs of each student, offer timely and helpful feedback and foster a friendly environment in the classroom (Chineta, 2023). Students' exposure to frequent teacher feedback is identified as one of the core teaching resources during the school period (Bonal & González, 2020). The effectiveness of feedback is measured by the amount of information provided to the learner regarding what they need to do to close the gaps in knowledge (Wisniewski et al., 2020). Feedback impacts on a wide range of dimensions, including cognitive skills, motivation and self-assessment skills (Henderson et al., 2019). When teachers give immediate feedback during a lesson, students are more likely to pause, interact and engage in conversation and alter their behaviour (Oke & Ijdshs, 2023). Feedback practice varies between individual teachers (Bergdahl & Nouri, 2021). Immediate feedback help learners to track the progress they are making (Ariffin et al., 2022).

VI. Methodology

The correlation research design was adopted for the study. It examines the relationships between two or more variables (Barkha, Lepcha & Shakeela, 2023). The population of the study consisted of 31506 respondents (1400 teachers and 30,106 students, source Bayelsa State Ministry of Education; EMIS, 2025). The proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to draw a sample size of 18 teachers and 376 students for the study. However, 360 copies of the instrument distributed were properly and correctly administered by the respondents, which represent 91.5%. This also implies that, 43 (8.5%) were not adequately administered by the respondents. Respondents were draw from the 41 public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area. Two research questions guided the study.

Two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of statistical significance. The instrument for data collection was developed by the researchers named "Classroom Organization and Students' Involvement Questionnaire (COSIQ)" formatted in four-point Rating scale. The instrument was validated by experts in educational management and measurement and evaluation all in the department of Educational Management in the Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. The internal consistency (reliability) of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach's alpha statistics and reliability coefficient of 0.86 for all the variables within the instrument. Mean ratings and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions. A criterion Mean of 2.50 was considered as basis for accepting or rejecting responses based on the extent of the relationship between classroom organization and students' involvement. Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) analysis was applied to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of statistical significance.

VII. Results

This section focuses on the empirical presentation of data, data analysis, summary of findings and discussion of findings.

Research Question One: What is the relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area.

Table 1: Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) scores of respondents on the relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills.

S/N	Items	N	X	SD	Remark
1.	To what extent do you think that teachers' use social interaction skills to effectively manage their classrooms.	360	3.11	.971	High Extent
2.	To what extent do you agree that disruptive behaviour of students in the classroom can be effectively managed and prevented by teachers using social interaction skills.	360	3.11	.884	High Extent
3.	To what extent do you believe that social interaction skills can be used to unite a diverse classroom, foster empathy and understanding among students.	360	3.12	.836	High Extent
4.	To what extent do you believe that social interaction skills can be used by teachers to promote teamwork among students, leading to successful group work.	360	3.16	.970	High Extent
Grand Mean			3.12	.915	High Extent

Criterion mean = 2.50; N = 360

The data presented in Table 1 showed mean scores of 3.11, 3.11, 3.12 and 3.16 for items 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The mean ratings for items 1, 2, 3 and 4 were higher than the criterion mean score of 2.50. An overall or grand mean score of 3.12 and a standard deviation score of .915 was obtained. The overall or grand mean score was higher than the criterion mean score of 2.50. The implication of this result is that there is a relationship between the variables and clear expectations and rules foster the development and inculcation of social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Consequently, after using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, the study progressed to utilize the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) analysis to evaluate whether the relationship between the variables is significant or not (see Table 4.3).

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area.

Table 2: Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) scores of respondents on the relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy.

S/N	Items	N	X	SD	Remark
5.	To what extent do you believe that how teachers manage their classrooms is influenced by immediate feedback strategies.	360	3.16	.859	High Extent
6.	To what extent do you feel that a productive classroom is influenced by teachers' use of immediate feedback strategies to manage their classrooms.	360	3.10	.927	High Extent
7.	To what extent do you think that addressing disruptive behaviour of students in the classroom is influenced by teachers' use of immediate feedback strategies.	360	3.06	.912	High Extent
8.	To what extent do you believe that students' needs and concerns can be better addressed by teachers who use immediate feedback strategies to manage their classrooms	360	3.12	.972	High Extent
Grand Mean			3.11	.918	High Extent

Criterion mean = 2.50; N = 360

The data presented in Table 2 showed mean scores of 3.16, 3.10, 3.06 and 3.12 for items 5, 6, 7 and 8 respectively. The mean ratings for items 5, 6, 7 and 8 were higher than the criterion mean score of 2.50. An overall or grand mean score of 3.11 and a standard deviation score of .918 was obtained. The overall or grand mean score was higher than the criterion mean score of 2.50. The implication of this result is that there is a relationship between the variables and effective behaviour management enhance immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Consequently, after using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, the study progressed to utilize the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) analysis to evaluate whether the relationship between the variables is significant or not (see Table 4.4).

Hypotheses 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) Analysis of the Relationship Between Clear Expectations and Rules and Social Interaction Skills

		Clear Expectations and Rules	Social Interaction Skills
Clear Expectations and Rules	Pearson Correlation	1	.203**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
Social Interaction Skills	Pearson Correlation	.203**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

* = . Significant at 0.05 alpha level; Degree of Freedom (df) = 358; N =360

The data presented in Table 4.3 revealed that, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) analysis is significant at 0.05 alpha level, because the calculated p-value of .000 is less than the criterion p-value of 0.05 alpha level with 358 degrees of freedom and correlation coefficient r value of .203. Hence the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State can be rejected. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a significant relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State is upheld.

Hypotheses 2

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) Analysis of the Relationship Between Effective Behaviour Management and Immediate Feedback Strategy

		Effective Behaviour Management	Immediate Feedback Strategies
Effective Behaviour Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.306**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
Immediate Feedback Strategy	Pearson Correlation	.306**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

* = . Significant at 0.05 alpha level; Degree of Freedom (df) = 358; N =360

The data presented in table 4 revealed that, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (PPMC) analysis is significant at 0.05 alpha level, because the calculated p-value of .000 is less than the criterion p-value of 0.05 alpha level with 358 degrees of freedom and correlation coefficient r value of .306. Hence the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State can be rejected. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a significant relationship between between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State is upheld.

VIII. Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between clear expectations and rules and social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, highlighted by mean scores that surpass the established criterion mean of 2.50 for all items assessed (3.13 for item 1, 3.04 for item 2, 3.04 for item 3, and 3.17 for item 4). The overall grand mean score of 3.09 further underscores this positive viewpoint, suggesting a strong acknowledgement of clear expectations and rules enhance social interaction skills in classroom management practices. The finding of this study is in line with the findings of Wang et al., (2020), who observed that clear expectations and rules can enable teachers fosters a positive classroom climate by being sensitive, responsive, and respectful of social and emotional needs, building relationships that reach beyond school interests, and incorporating students' perspectives into learning activities.

The findings of the study also revealed that there is a relationship between effective behaviour management and immediate feedback strategies in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, highlighted by mean scores that surpass the established criterion mean of 2.50 for all items assessed

(3.16 for item 5, 3.10 for item 6, 3.06 for item 7, and 3.12 for item 8). The overall grand mean score of 3.11 further underscores this positive viewpoint, suggesting a strong awareness of effective behaviour management as a timely evaluation tool for promoting immediate feedback strategies in teachers' classroom management practices. The finding of this study is in compliance with the findings of Ong and Quek (2023), who also observed that when teachers provide timely feedback to students and involve them in the feedback process, a supportive learning environment is created which promotes the learning motivation (Ong & Quek, 2023).

IX. Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrated that there is a relationship between the variables and clear expectations and rules foster the development and inculcation of social interaction skills in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Teachers' ability to use interpersonal skills to manage their classrooms effectively depends on setting clear expectation and rules. It was also concluded that there is a relationship between the variables and effective behaviour management enhance immediate feedback strategy in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Teachers can use effective behaviour management as a timely evaluation tool to effectively manage students' immediate feedback strategies in the classrooms.

X. Recommendations

1. Teachers can use clear expectations and rules to successfully manage their classrooms, by creating a friendly classroom culture among students.
2. Teachers can integrate social interaction skills into their classroom organization practice to enable students relate effectively with their teachers and peers.
3. Teachers can employ effective behaviour management to facilitate prompt feedback in managing students' academic activities and behaviour in the classroom.
4. Teachers should interfuse immediate feedback strategies to address learning gaps, by motivating and engaging their students.

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